

A Consortium in the NFDI

PUNCH4NFDI

Particles, Universe, NuClei and Hadrons for the NFDI

DELIVERABLE REPORT

DEMONSTRATOR FOR A FEDERATED COMPUTE INFRASTRUCTURE

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Deliverable:

Demonstrator for the federated compute infrastructure Compute4PUNCH.

Executive summary:

A detailed description of the federated compute infrastructure made available to the PUNCH4NFDI consortium, Compute4PUNCH, is provided.

The federation of the available compute resources is based on a single overlay batch system defining a single pool of resources whose provisioning is ensured by a meta-scheduler. This is realised by using the HTCondor batch system, the COBaID/TARDIS meta-scheduler and the Apptainer container technology.

The provisioning of entry points is based on traditional login nodes running the HTCondor suite and enabling the users to submit jobs to the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure. The access to the entry points is standardised using access tokens based on the OIDC protocol and provisioned by the Helmholtz AAI provider.

The scalable provisioning of the workflow-specific software environments is based on the Apptainer container technology and the use of the CERN Virtual Machine File System CVMFS from which the workflow-specific containers are retrieved when the HTCondor jobs are executed.

The refreshment of access tokens required to access the storage resources of the PUNCH4NFDI consortium is based on the Mytoken service that delivers credential artifacts allowing to refresh access tokens without resorting to the users. The implementation in the HTCondor suite makes use of a producer and a monitoring plugins taking care of the OIDC flow in a way transparent to the users.

In addition to the description of the demonstrator, this report also describes some additional developments, namely the integration of additional compute resources into the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure, the development of user workflows and the integration of the access token-based HTCondor software suite in the REANA analysis platform in collaboration with the TA4 WP4 working group responsible for the development of the PUNCH4NFDI Data Portal.

1 INTRODUCTION

The federated compute infrastructure made available to the PUNCH community via the PUNCH4NFDI consortium, Compute4PUNCH, aims at providing a seamless, federated and standardised access to the collection of compute resources provided by the participating institutions. The completion of this infrastructure is seeking to cover the variety of computing needs of the different communities while minimizing the potential modifications to be adopted by the resource providers. Reaching these two competing goals is made possible using state-of-the-art technologies and is driven by the experience gained by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and the Scientific Computing Centre (SCC) in the establishment of compute infrastructures for the High Energy Physics (HEP) communities.

The federation of the High-Throughput Compute (HTC), High-Performance Compute (HPC) and Cloud resources supplied by the PUNCH4NFDI participating communities is realised by performing a dynamic and transparent integration of these resources into one federated HTCondor-based [1] overlay batch system (OBS) using the COBaID/TARDIS resource meta-scheduler [2] [3] [4] [5].

The standardisation of the access to the federated compute resources is realised by using a token-based Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) that enables to overcome the challenge of having different authentication mechanisms for the different resource providers. The access to the login nodes providing entry points to the federated compute resources is making use of this token-based AAI, as well as the access to the federated storage resources.

The delivery of community-specific software environments is achieved by relying on container technologies whose scalable provisioning is ensured using the CERN Virtual Machine File System (CVMFS) [6].

The federation of the compute resources made available to the PUNCH4NFDI consortium by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and the Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität (WWU) in Münster, their standardised access relying on a token-based AAI, the provisioning of entry points and the scalable delivery of the required software environments are the four pillars of the demonstrator for the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure.

In addition to the description of the demonstrator, this report also describes some additional developments, namely the integration of additional compute resources into the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure, the development of user workflows and the integration of the access token-based HTCondor software suite in the REANA [7] analysis platform in collaboration with the TA4 WP4 working group.

2 DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE DELIVERABLE

2.1 FEDERATION OF THE COMPUTE RESOURCES

The HTC, HPC and Cloud compute resources provided by the PUNCH4NFDI institutions distributed all over Germany are highly heterogeneous and characterised by a variety of architectures, operating systems and software environments. The supplied resources are furthermore already in operation and most often utilised by different communities which may have made different choices for the authentication methods, the acceptable use policies (AUP) and batch systems. Their integration in the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure should therefore interfere as little as possible with their operational status and minimise the number of modifications the providers may have to apply to their systems. This goal is achieved by relying on existing technologies recently developed for the federated computing infrastructures of the German High Energy Physics community, and by adapting and extending them to cover the specific needs of PUNCH4NFDI. Using the technologies developed in the framework of the HEP computing community does not only allow to perform a transparent integration of the resources made available to PUNCH4NFDI but offers in addition the opportunity to maximise the synergies wherever possible.

The two key ingredients underlying the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure are the aggregation of the available compute resources in a single overlay batch system (OBS) forming a single federated pool of resources and the provisioning and deprovisioning of these resources by a meta-scheduler. The HTCondor Software Suite, a specialised batch system for compute-intensive jobs specifically designed to allow for a dynamic extension of its pool of resources, has been chosen to aggregate the resources in a single OBS. The actual integration of a given resource is achieved by executing placeholder jobs, known as pilots or drones, on that resource. Each drone is running an instance of the HTCondor startd daemon which presents the resource to the federated pool as a machine capable of running jobs, also known as execution point or worker node. The startd daemon also advertises some of the worker node attributes to the federated pool, allowing for a late binding of the actual jobs in the queue to the most appropriate integrated resource. The drones rely on the Apptainer [8] container technology natively supported by the HTCondor software suite to provide the worker node environment suited for the applications of the PUNCH4NFDI consortium. They are stored in a common GitLab repository hosted at the Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics in Potsdam (AIP) and accessible to all Compute4PUNCH resource providers.

The configurations of the HTCondor daemons contained in the drones are also made available in a common GitLab repository hosted at the AIP and accessible to the resource providers. At the time of a resource integration, configurations are pulled from this repository to the drones using a dedicated HTCondor tool [9] that allows to dynamically configure an HTCondor node from a git repository. The HTCondor central manager - that runs the HTCondor collector and negotiator daemons, defines the

extent of the federated pool and centralises the information about its state - is hosted at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. Its configuration is managed and deployed using the configuration management tool Puppet and the system management software Red Hat Satellite. Worker nodes made available to Compute4PUNCH by a given resource provider authenticate to the HTCondor central manager via the use of IDTOKENS that are provided on request to the resource provider at the time of the first integration of their resource in the federated infrastructure.

The second key ingredient of the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure is the COBaID/TARDIS meta-scheduler that provisions and deprovisions resources according to the actual need. COBaID/TARDIS takes the decision to either extend or reduce the number of integrated resources displaying specific sets of attributes based on the current utilisation of these kinds of resources. The Compute4PUNCH infrastructure at the level of a given resource provider comprises an instance of the COBaID/TARDIS meta-scheduler acting as an interface between the local batch system or cloud API and the overlay batch system. The Opportunistic Balancing Daemon COBaID takes care of matching the actual demand for a given type of resources, while the TARDIS plugin provides a collection of site adapters that allow the management of resources through the means of the most used batch systems. This management includes the provisioning and deprovisioning of resources and their integration in the OBS.

In the framework of the Compute4PUNCH demonstrator, compute resources from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and the Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität (WWU) in Münster have been integrated in the compute infrastructure. At KIT, two compute clusters have been integrated using a dedicated fairshare between the different users. The first one is the local university cluster TOPAS (Throughput Optimized Analysis System) [10] that provides 8 NVidia V100 Graphics Processing Units (GPU) with 64 cores each and 160 GB of shared RAM to PUNCH4NFDI. The second one is the GridKa cluster [11] that provides up to 2000 cores with 2-3 GB of shared RAM per core to PUNCH4NFDI. In Münster, compute resources from the WWU OpenStack Cloud have been integrated in the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure.

In addition to these resources integrated in the framework of the demonstrator, compute resources are now also provided to the PUNCH4NFDI consortium by the Georg-August-Universität (GAU) in Göttingen, the Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität (LMU) in München and the Leibniz-Rechenzentrum (LRZ) Compute Cloud in Garching.

2.2 PROVISIONING OF ENTRY POINTS

The transparent and dynamic integration of compute resources in the Compute4PUNCH federated infrastructure presented in the first section was dealing with the community of resource providers. This section is dealing with the community

of resource users to which the available resources should be presented transparently via the provisioning of a collection of entry points. As of today, this collection is limited to a single login node running the RHEL8 operating system and hosted at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. This login node, also known as submit node or access point in the HTCondor framework, runs an instance of the HTCondor schedd daemon and holds the queue of compute jobs submitted by the users. At the event of a compute job submission, the schedd daemon presents the requests for resources to the federated pool and stores and manages the jobs in the queue. As in the case of a worker node, a login node authenticates to the HTCondor central manager via the use of IDTOKENS provided on request to the login node provider at the time of its first integration in the federated infrastructure.

The access to the future instances of entry points is standardised and relies on the use of tokens, such that the users can connect to the instances using a single authentication mechanism already in use to access the existing login node at KIT. This mechanism is based on the Open ID Connect (OIDC) identity and authentication protocol [12] and is using the Helmholtz AAI [13] as the identity and authorisation management (IAM) system to arbitrate the access to the login node. The Helmholtz AAI is based on the Unity IdM [14] identity and authentication service and follows the AARC Blueprint architecture [15]. The key ingredients of the authentication mechanism based on the use of OIDC tokens are described below.

From the client side, users first register once to the Helmholtz AAI provider and locally install the `oidc-agent` [16], a set of tools to manage OIDC tokens and handle them from the command line in a similar way as are handled SSH keys. The `oidc-agent` being locally installed, users configure the agent once using their account at the Helmholtz AAI provider. The connection to the login node can then be established by installing and using the `mccli` client [17], a wrapper around the SSH client that enables to settle a SSH connection using OIDC access tokens. In summary, after having registered once to the Helmholtz AAI provider and installed once the required software mentioned above, users will be able to connect to all available instances of entry points using the `mccli` client with OIDC access tokens provided by the Helmholtz AAI in a similar way as they would establish a traditional SSH connection.

From the server side, the login node is running the `motley cue` [18] service that maps federated OIDC identities to local identities on the node, and the `pam-ssh-oidc` [19] module, a pluggable authentication module (PAM) plugged to the SSH daemon that accepts OIDC access tokens for the authentication of users - connecting to the login node via the OIDC-enabled SSH client `mccli`. The `motley cue` service comprises, among others, a local user management (LUM) module that acts as an interface between `motley cue` and the local user management system and handles the lifecycle of the local user accounts mapped to the federated OIDC identities.

The `motley cue` LUM module offers several backend plugins for the integration with various local user management systems. The login node is currently hosting local

UNIX accounts and the motley cue LUM interface is therefore configured to use the local UNIX backend. As in the case of a worker node, the configuration of the login node is managed and deployed using the configuration management tool Puppet and the system management software Red Hat Satellite.

2.3 PROVISIONING OF SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENTS

The provisioning of specific operating systems and software environments that cover the various needs of the different PUNCH4NFDI communities relies on the Apptainer [8] container technology and the use of the CERN Virtual Machine File System CVMFS [6]. The operating systems and software environments are defined by the users and provisioned based on the following workflow: once the users have defined the container build instructions necessary to execute their analysis on the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure, the files containing these instructions - also known as Docker files - are stored in a common GitLab repository, the Container Stack repository [20], hosted at the AIP in Potsdam. A Continuous Integration/Continuous Development (CI/CD) workflow is checking the validity of the build instructions provided by the users, integrating security updates when required, to finally build the containers and upload them to a common GitLab Container Registry [21] hosted at the AIP. A transparent and scalable provisioning of the available containers is then ensured by converting them into the Apptainer unpacked format before making them available to the compute infrastructure - with a latency of the order of a few hours - using the CERN CVMFS repository `unpacked.cern.ch`. Depending on the resource provider, the CVMFS file system is either directly installed on the bare-metal or mounted using a mount namespace. When later submitting a specific job to the Compute4PUNCH HTCondor batch system, the users will only need to specify in the job configuration file the name of the container to be retrieved from CVMFS to run their analysis. Workflow examples are provided in a repository of the PUNCH4NFDI GitLab instance for the users to familiarise with the provisioning described above.

Several workflows making use of diverse containers have been tested on the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure. Among others, the calibration of the Two-meter Sky Survey data from the LOFAR (LOw Frequency ARray) radio telescope [22] and the processing of cosmological model simulations have been actively tested by the community from the Thüringer Landessternwarte (TLS), while the reduction of interferometric data from the MeerKAT radio telescope [23] has been processed by the community from the Universitätssternwarte München (USM). Running these workflows has shed some light on differences between the way data are processed in HEP and astrophysics analysis, and the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure has shown to be able to adapt to serve the needs of both communities. The collaboration with the USM team has led to the extension of the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure through the federation of new resources provided by the Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität (LMU) in München. The collaboration with the TLS team has shown the need to provide powerful multicore single nodes with a scratch space as large as 5 to 10 TB, the way the LOFAR data are processed being to some extent at the intersection

between High-Throughput and High-Performance computing. The way input data are accessed can also exhibit differences between HEP and astrophysics analysis. Considering again the LOFAR calibration workflow as an illustrative example, the input data are in that case only available on tapes. Their local copy to a dCache storage system at KIT and their provisioning to the worker nodes using a NFS distributed file system is the solution implemented so far to tackle this specific data access mode. As demonstrated by the above workflows, the interactions between the Compute4PUNCH developers and the communities of users have played an important role in the latest developments of the compute infrastructure.

2.4 MANAGEMENT OF ACCESS TOKENS

The access to the federated storage resources Storage4PUNCH is standardised by using a token-based AAI that provides a single authentication mechanism for the collection of storage resources. As for the login nodes, this mechanism is based on the OIDC protocol and is using the Helmholtz AAI provider as the identity and authorisation management system to arbitrate the access to the storage resources. For the purpose of preventing or at least limiting malicious use of the PUNCH4NFDI resources, OIDC access tokens obtained from the Helmholtz AAI provider have a limited lifetime of just over an hour. This value being shorter than the average job run-time, a mechanism had to be introduced within the HTCondor framework to refresh access tokens on the fly on the actual worker nodes running the jobs. The HTCondor Credential daemon Credd provides advanced features to refresh access tokens on the worker nodes via the use of Credential Monitoring (CredMon) plugins running on the submit node. The Credd daemon is agnostic to the type of tokens and only used for their distribution. The CredMon plugins are specific to the type of tokens and responsible for their manipulation and refreshment. A specific CredMon plugin had therefore to be developed to manipulate and refresh OIDC access tokens provided by the Helmholtz AAI. This plugin makes use of a service developed at the SCC, the Mytoken service, that aims at provisioning long-running compute jobs with OIDC access tokens in an easy and secure way [24]. The Mytoken service provides credential artifacts known as mytokens that allow a client application, the Helmholtz AAI provider, to provision new access tokens without resorting to the user. The mytoken credentials are like OIDC refresh tokens which they supersede by enabling the enforcement of additional restrictions on the provided access tokens, among others regarding their lifetime, provided scopes, geolocation or audience claims.

The production and refreshment workflows are implemented as follows. A plugin, known as the MytokenProducer [25] and based on the Mytoken libraries, is invoked during the HTCondor submission step to prompt the user to create a mytoken credential. This plugin enables the user to obtain a mytoken by authenticating once to the Mytoken web service via a Helmholtz AAI OIDC flow. The mytoken obtained that way is encrypted, securely stored on the submit node and used to create the first access token. This access token is stored on the submit node as well and made available to the HTCondor compute job on the specific worker node where this job is

running. The mytoken object, residing only on the submit node, is not exposed to the world. It can therefore be used during a relatively long period of time, typically of the order of a week, to refresh the OIDC access tokens embedded in the HTCondor compute jobs on the worker nodes. A plugin, known as the MyTokenCredMon [26], is periodically invoked by the HTCondor suite to check the validity of the OIDC access tokens. When these are about to expire, the plugin replaces them by new access tokens via a Helmholtz AAI OIDC flow arbitrated by the Mytoken service. The new credentials are saved on the submit node and made available to the HTCondor Cred daemon that distributes them to all HTCondor Starters currently executing jobs of a particular user. This procedure ensures a long-term access to the Storage4PUNCH resources for the jobs running on the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure in a way transparent to the users. When a compute job is finalised, a file transfer service available in the HTCondor software can be used to transfer the job output to the Storage4PUNCH resources, using the Helmholtz AAI access token embedded in the job to authenticate to the storage element.

It must be noted that the MytokenProducer can also be used - to create a mytoken credential together with the first access token - outside of the HTCondor software suite to allow for an automated submission of a collection of compute jobs. Besides its use within the PUNCH4NFDI community, the HTCondor release implementing the production and monitoring of OIDC access tokens using the Mytoken service is also deployed by other scientific communities outside the PUNCH4NFDI consortium. It is used by the DARWIN (dark matter wimp search with liquid xenon) collaboration [27] and its deployment at the NIKHEF Computer Technology department in Amsterdam is work in progress.

2.5 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES

The TA2 WP2 working group responsible for the development of the PUNCH4NFDI compute infrastructure is actively collaborating with the TA4 WP4 working group responsible for the development of the PUNCH4NFDI Data Portal. This portal will define the single entry point to the research products to be delivered by the PUNCH4NFDI community, with a research product being defined as the complete collection of information related to a given analysis. A typical research product encompasses data, simulation, code, executable, workflow description, metadata and publication. A pillar of the Data Portal is the use of the Reproducible research data analysis platform REANA [7]. This analysis platform developed at CERN provides advanced features particularly suited for the development of research products. It offers a wrapper around computational workflow engines and a scalable model to use remote compute resources. It uses containers to run the analysis workflows, ensuring in that way interoperability and reusability, and presents a user-friendly graphical interface allowing access to the collection of information required to build a research product. The REANA platform provides several compute backends, known as job controllers, that are responsible for the execution and the management of the jobs on the compute resources. Job controllers are available for the HTCondor and Slurm

batch systems and for the Kubernetes containerized workflow management system. The compute backend for the HTCondor batch system available in REANA does not meet the PUNCH4NFDI requirements related to the authentication and authorization infrastructure, for it uses the ticket-based Kerberos authentication protocol instead of the token-based OIDC protocol used by the PUNCH4NFDI compute and storage resources. Our collaboration with the TA4 WP4 working group and more specifically with the team from the Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics in Potsdam (AIP) is focused on the integration of the PUNCH4NFDI HTCondor software suite into the REANA analysis platform through the development of a specific job controller using the Helmholtz AAI OIDC flow. A REANA production instance is hosted and managed by the AIP in Potsdam that has setup a REANA test instance for the purpose of the integration. The PUNCH4NFDI-specific job controller [28] that is now part of the official REANA software release has been tested extensively in the submission of REANA jobs to the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure. The actual OIDC workflow is currently implemented as follows. Before submitting a REANA job, the user runs a dedicated executable [29] that produces and monitors a mytoken object, saves an encrypted version of it locally and uploads to the REANA server an unencrypted version in the form of a REANA secret. The job controller later invokes a second executable [30] that uploads the mytoken from the REANA server to the login node from which the HTCondor job associated to the REANA workflow is submitted. When the compute job is finalised, the job output is transferred to both the Storage4PUNCH resources and the REANA workspace where a direct access to the analysis results is possible via the REANA graphical user interface.

3 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PLANS

The developments accomplished within the TA2 WP2 working group have been presented, together with its interactions with the actual designers of the workflows to be submitted on the Compute4PUNCH infrastructure, and its collaboration with the TA4 WP4 working group responsible for the access to the research products associated to the workflows. The federation of the compute resources has been established and efforts to federate new resources are in progress. The provisioning of single entry points and compute environments has been made available to the PUNCH4NFDI consortium and actively tested and used for the submission of various workflows. The management of an OIDC-based AAI has been developed and implemented in the HTCondor batch system. Plans include the use of Mytoken credential artifacts to authenticate job submissions to the HTCondor software, the development of a file transfer service within the HTCondor software based on the XRootD data access software suite [31], the integration of the Helmholtz AAI OIDC flow in the REANA client and the provisioning of shared home directories to the PUNCH4NFDI users.

4 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] HTCondor Team, *HTCondor* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397217>.
- [2] M. Fischer, E. Kuehn, M. Giffels, M. Schnepf, S. Kroboth, T. M., O. Freyermuth, *Matterminers/cobald: v0.14.0* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199049>.
- [3] M. Fischer, E. Kuehn, M. Giffels, M.J. Schnepf, A. Petzold, A. Heiss, *EPJ Web of Conferences*, 245, 07040 (2020).
- [4] M. Giffels, M. Fischer, A. Haas, S. Kroboth, M. Schnepf, E. Kuehn, M. Schuhmacher, R. Caspart, F. von Cube, D. Sammel et al., *Matterminers/tardis: 0.7.1* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7943895>.
- [5] M. Fischer, M. Giffels, A. Heiss, E. Kuehn, M. Schnepf, R.F. von Cube, A. Petzold, G. Quast, *EPJ Web of Conferences*, 245, 07038 (2020).
- [6] CVMFS, <https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [7] REANA, <https://reanahub.io>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [8] Apptainer Container System, <https://apptainer.org/>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [9] *condor-git-config: dynamically configure an HTCondor node from a git repository*, <https://github.com/MatterMiners/condor-git-config>.
- [10] R. Caspart, M. Fischer, M. Giffels, R.F. von Cube, C. Heidecker, E. Kuehn, G. Quast, A. Heiss, A. Petzold, *EPJ Web of Conferences*, 245, 07007 (2020).
- [11] GridKa, <https://www.scc.kit.edu/en/research/gridka.php>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [12] What is OpenID Connect, <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [13] Helmholtz Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure, <https://hifis.net/aai>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [14] Unity Authentication and identity management, <https://unity-idm.eu>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [15] AARC Blueprint Architecture (BPA), <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [16] oidc-agent, <https://indigo-dc.gitbook.io/oidc-agent>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [17] mccli, <https://mccli.readthedocs.io/en/latest>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [18] motley cue, <https://motley-cue.readthedocs.io/en/latest>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [19] ssh-oidc, <https://github.com/EOSC-synergy/ssh-oidc>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [20] PUNCH4NFDI Container Stacks, <https://gitlab-p4n.aip.de/compute4punch/container-stacks>, accessed on 30.09.2024.

- [21] PUNCH4NFDI Container Registry, https://gitlab-p4n.aip.de/compute4punch/container-stacks/container_registry, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [22] LOFAR radio telescope, <https://www.astron.nl/telescopes/lofar>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [23] MeerKAT radio telescope, <https://www.sarao.ac.za/science/meerkat>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [24] Mytoken Service, <https://mytoken.data.kit.edu>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [25] C4P HTCondor Producer, <https://gitlab.kit.edu/benoit.roland/C4P-HTCondor-Producer>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [26] C4P HTCondor Credmon, <https://gitlab.kit.edu/benoit.roland/C4P-HTCondor-Credmon>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [27] DARWIN, <https://darwin.physik.uzh.ch/index.html>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [28] COMPUTE4PUNCH REANA Job Controller, <https://github.com/giffels/reana-job-controller/tree/add/compute4punch-support>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [29] COMPUTE4PUNCH REANA Producer, <https://gitlab-p4n.aip.de/compute4punch/C4P-REANA-Producer>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [30] COMPUTE4PUNCH REANA Upload, <https://gitlab-p4n.aip.de/compute4punch/C4P-REANA-Upload>, accessed on 30.09.2024.
- [31] XRootD, <https://xrootd.slac.stanford.edu>, accessed on 30.09.2024.

5 ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Development
CVMFS	CERN Virtual Machine File System
HTCondor	High-Throughput Computing batch system
IAM	Identity and Authorisation Management
LUM	Local User Management
OBS	Overlay Batch System
OIDC	Open ID Connect - identity and authentication protocol
REANA	Reproducible research data analysis platform
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management